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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Xb
by S. Söderhjelm, Lund Observatory

Some further tests of different solution-procedures with the new STDDBLS program have been made for simulated runs with only a single year of observations available.

1. Introduction

In NDAC/LO/122, a '3-stage' procedure was proposed when running STDDBLS. The simulation-tests showed the feasibility of the method, but so far only for the 'final' reductions, with 2.5 years of observations available. A more urgent question is how STDDBLS is best used after the first year of observations. We need to know e.g. if it is possible to identify 'definitive' 1-year solutions where the final (2.5-year) runs may be made with 'mini'-meshes consisting of their center-points only. Maybe the *primary* positions may be trusted even if the position of a faint secondary is indeterminate? What C_i -values may be used, and is there an alternative to the '3-stage' procedure? Some preliminary answers to these questions are given below.

2. 1-year runs of STDDBLS

As in NDAC/LO/114, the main difference in simulating observations for 1 year only is the increased attitude-errors. As a rough model, all attitude mean errors are doubled as compared with the standard 2.5 year case. In this way, I have simulated 400+200 systems, all with $H_p=8.5$ for the primary component. The 400 ones in Ser. 1 have separations in the range 1-10 arcsec (single IDT pointing), while the 200 systems in Ser. 2 are with individual IDT pointings and separations 10-30 arcsec. In all cases, the (1-axis) position mean error was taken as 1.0 arcsec for the primary, 0.7 arcsec for the secondary (relative to the primary), giving a variety of actual primary and relative errors. The systems were uniformly distributed over the sky, and the magnitude-differences were uniformly distributed between 0 and 4 mag.

In preliminary experiments, I used the '3-stage' procedure, and a variety of C_i -values. Checking only the total number of 'false' solutions (primary or secondary position error above 0.4 arcsec), it was apparent that the actual C_i -values were not very important. Around 25-30% of the systems get false solutions, for any reasonable choice of the C_i :s. This is of course expected, because the scanning-geometry for low-latitude systems will often give a number of spurious solutions with almost as good fit as the real ones. The '3-stage' method also seemed a bit too elaborate, and I started to try some simpler alternatives.

The simplest way is of course to run all systems with the same mesh-size and the same C_i -parameters. This gives somewhat poorer results, and the computing-times are some 40 % larger than for the '3-stage' method. An alternative '2-stage'

method may be a good compromise (more efficient than a '1-stage' procedure, simpler to program than the '3-stage' one), but at the price of introducing more C_i -parameters. In the first stage, the C_1 and C_2 are rather small, and as before, the 'final' solutions with fits below C_4 are accepted 'directly'. At the end of the mesh-searches, the 'best' solution is accepted only if it has a fit below C_3 , and the ones with a poorer fit (or with no final solution at all) are passed through 'stage 2'. The mesh-sizes are normally the same as in 'stage 1', but the C_1 - C_3 parameters are larger, allowing more solutions to be tested. In all, sixteen C_i 's have to be specified (4 per stage and different ones for close and wide systems), precluding all attempts at a complete optimization. As will be seen below, however, the parameter-choices are not critical. (Another improvement of the program is a check that the final primary and secondary positions are offset from their a priori values by no more than the size of the search-mesh used. In a few cases, this prevents gross errors).

3. Solution results

The methods described above have been applied to different subsets of the simulated systems, and it is difficult to make strictly valid comparisons. The '3-stage method' was tested first on 100 'close' systems and 50 'wide' ones. A good parameter-set for the close ones (among some 4-6 tried) was $C_1=100.$, $C_2=3.0$, $C_3=1.7$ (stage 1+2), $C_1=100.$, $C_2=2.5$, $C_3=1.2$ (stage 3), and a dividing $\Delta m=2.0$. For the wide ones, the corresponding data were $C_1=50.$, $C_2=2.0$, $C_3=1.2$ (stage 1+2) or 0.9 (stage 3) and a dividing $\Delta m=2.5$. Using these values on all the simulated systems, I obtained 296 correct solutions, 97 false ones, and 7 with no solution (Ser. 1). The total computing time was 1044 minutes. For Ser. 2, the corresponding figures are 135 correct, 65 false, in 959 minutes. (In the last case, however, it was apparent that the C_3 -value in stage 1 was too high, admitting a too large number of false solutions).

The '2-stage' method was also tested with several parameter-choices, but again the numbers of correct and false solutions stayed rather constant. One gets more correct solutions by using smaller C_3 and C_4 , but only at the cost of greatly increased computing times. For Ser. 1, we get 304 correct and 90 false solutions in 851 minutes [$C_i=40.$, 1.8, 1.6, 1.3 (stage 1); 100., 5.0, 2.1, 1.3 (stage 2)]. An 'optimal' run [$C_i=50.$, 1.7, 1.4, 1.1 (stage 1); 125., 5.0, 1.9, 1.1 (stage 2)] produces 314 correct and 80 false ones, but the computing time has doubled to 1667 minutes. For Ser. 2, this is even more apparent. We get 148 correct and 52 false solutions in 421 minutes [$C_i=20.$, 1.5, 1.3, 1.0 (stage 1); 50., 3.0, 1.6, 1.0 (stage 2)], while the 'best' run [$C_i=15.$, 1.4, 1.15, 0.85 (stage 1); 38., 3.0, 1.5, 0.85 (stage 2)] gives 152 correct and 47 false (and one with no solution) in 997 minutes.

All the runs so far are with a mesh-step of 0.50 arcsec. This value may also be optimized, as can be seen from the results in Table 1. The same C_i -values as for the 'best' runs above were used, and it is seen that for Ser. 1, a slightly smaller mesh-step than 0.50 arcsec might be used (CPU-time permitting..), while for the wider systems of Ser. 2, a larger value is only advantageous. (These 'optimizations' depend, however, on the a priori position uncertainties assumed, because these determine the size of the search meshes. The number of mesh-points required to reach e.g. 3 arcsec is a step-function of g).

Table 1a. Solution statistics and total CPU-time for 'optimal' Ser. 1 solutions as a function of the mesh-step.

g(arcsec)	failed	false	OK	CPU(min)
0.45	5	79	316	2104
0.50	6	80	314	1667
0.55	7	83	310	1442
0.60	13	84	303	(<1340)

Table 1b. Solution statistics and total CPU-time for 'optimal' Ser. 2 solutions as a function of the mesh-step.

g(arcsec)	failed	false	OK	CPU(min)
0.45	2	47	151	1316
0.50	1	47	152	997
0.55	1	46	153	849
0.60	3	51	146	(<850)

4. Identifying the correct solutions

As seen from the data above, some 20-25% of the solutions are 'false', that is, the primary or relative positions deviate from their true values by more than 0.4 arcsec. Also, as shown in Fig. 1, it is generally *not* possible to identify these false solutions from the observed fits to the observations. The S_f -values show almost the same distribution for the false as for the correct solutions. At low latitudes and/or large magnitude differences, however, the proportion of false solutions is higher, and an obvious question is whether it is possible to find an area in the eclat- Δm plane with only correct solutions. Fig 2 shows all 142 false solutions from the 'minimum time' runs, and as expected, they cluster along the low-latitude/high Δm borders. (Curiously, the stars closest to the ecliptic poles also often give false solutions). Disregarding a very few points, we may say with good confidence that a solution for a system with $\Delta m < 2.5$ and ecliptic latitude 25-80 degrees is correct. Plotting the correct solutions (Fig 3), the reverse is not true. A solution for a low-latitude and/or high Δm system may or may not be correct.

Fig. 1. Position-errors (sol-true, pr and rel) for all the solutions as a function of the normalized fit to the observations.

Fig. 2. Distribution of the false solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the true solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

Looking again at the false solutions, plots of the primary and relative errors versus the ecliptic latitude show that almost all *primary* positions are correct whenever the ecliptic latitude is above 30 degrees.

5. Conclusions

The main conclusions from the above would be the following. First, a large number of 'methods' and parameter choices will give similar results when observations for one year only are available. The limited 'resolution' is inherent in the observations, and rather little can be done to decrease the ratio of false to correct solutions. In practice, after 1 year, we will use e.g. the '2-stage' method to derive a set of preliminary solutions to the known systems. The search-mesh size will be chosen for each system according to a priori estimates of the maximum position errors expected, and the number of completely failed solutions is expected to be small. The majority of the resulting solutions are expected to be 'good', but there is no certain way of telling which are not.

For the systems in the 'safe' $eclat-\Delta m$ range, the preliminary solutions may be used as definitive start values in the final solutions after 2.5 years. A special program with *no* mesh searches could be used to very rapidly give the final solutions. For the many thousands of systems where the 1-year solution may be in error (and for the few with no preliminary solutions), new runs of STDDBLs *with* large search-meshes are required. At high latitudes, the primary mesh could be shrunk to zero, but otherwise unbiased searches for both the primary and the relative positions should be made. As shown in NDAC/LO/122, such final 2.5 year runs are expected to give correct solutions for the great majority of systems.

For completeness, some 1-year solutions should be tried also for appreciably brighter and fainter systems than the standard 8.5 mag. Such simulations are planned for Paper Xc.